

The PlasmaPy Project

Building an Open Source Software Ecosystem for Plasma Research and Education

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Major changes in versions 2 and 3: Updates to the cost range section and the addition of an appendix of responses to the expert group evaluation.

Goals of Initiative

- Develop **PlasmaPy** as an open source Python package for plasma science containing the functionality needed by most plasma physicists across disciplines;
- Create an open source software ecosystem for plasma science containing affiliated packages with more specialized functionality;
- Increase research efficiency, improve scientific reproducibility, and facilitate greater societal impact of plasma physics; and
- Use modern best practices from scientific programming and computer science to produce readable, reliable, and maintainable code.

Description of the Initiative

Motivation

Software is crucial to all areas of modern plasma science research. Laboratory plasma physicists use software to interpret plasma diagnostics, analyze experimental results, and glean insights using advanced data science techniques. Space scientists use software to reduce and understand *in situ* observations. Numericists use software to simulate the behavior of laboratory, heliospheric, and astrophysical plasmas. Theorists use computer algebra systems to perform or check derivations. Cross-disciplinary research and cross-comparisons between experiments, observations, simulations, and theories all require software. **Despite the**

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fundamental importance of software throughout plasma physics, there have been few visible efforts by the community to collaborate on a common open source codebase.

The lack of a common shared open source framework has resulted in several adverse consequences. Different researchers and groups frequently duplicate software with essentially the same functionality. These different software packages typically lack interoperability, thus impeding interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary collaboration. Access to these codes is frequently restricted in some way. Packages tend to be difficult to install, especially if they depend on external libraries. Pressure to publish leads to code written in a rush to get the next research paper out. Documentation is frequently a low priority. Packages often lack a testing framework, preventing subtle and often critical bugs from being found before affecting results. Most scientific programmers are self-taught, and constant time pressure prevents us from taking time to learn new programming skills and best practices for scientific computing. The combination of all of these factors leads to the following consequences.

1. It is difficult for newcomers to begin research in plasma physics.
2. Cross-disciplinary research is hampered due to the lack of interoperability.
3. Reproducing plasma research is time-consuming and difficult (if not outright impossible).

Over the past decade, researchers in different scientific disciplines have collaboratively developed open source Python packages for their fields. Examples include [Astropy](#), [SunPy](#), [Heliopy](#), [SpacePy](#), [pysat](#), [scikit-rf](#), [MetPy](#), [Biopython](#), and [PsychoPy](#). These packages provide essential functionality, frameworks for data analysis and visualization, and educational resources. Projects like these are transforming the way scientific research is being done by making it more open, collaborative, auditable, and reproducible. The Astropy core package contains functionality needed by most astronomers across subfields. Astropy's affiliated packages contain more specialized functionality. Astropy's coordination committee regulates open development and intercompatibility among the core and affiliated packages. **Astropy and its affiliated packages constitute an open source software ecosystem for astronomy.** The [Python in Heliophysics Community](#) has similarly begun fostering an open source software ecosystem for solar physics and space science (e.g., [Burrell et al. 2018](#)).

The open source revolution that is well underway in astronomy and heliophysics is only just beginning in plasma science. **PlasmaPy is an open source software package for plasma physics in the early stages of development.** PlasmaPy began in 2017 to provide the foundation of a software framework for plasma physics that is intercompatible with the astronomy and heliophysics software ecosystems. The version 0.2 development release of PlasmaPy in May 2019 serves as an invitation to the plasma physics community to participate in the development of an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics.

Status of the PlasmaPy core package as of version 0.2.0

The `atomic` subpackage provides functional and object-oriented interfaces to access properties of atoms, ions, isotopes, and other particles. The `atomic` subpackage is used by most plasma parameter and transport coefficient functions because particle properties such as charge and mass are needed to describe every plasma. The `physics` subpackage contains

functions related to plasma parameters and dimensionless quantities. The `mathematics` subpackage contains commonly needed functions such as the plasma dispersion function. The `transport` subpackage allows calculation of plasma transport coefficients using a variety of models. We have begun developing a `diagnostics` subpackage which includes prototype classes for Langmuir probe analysis. The `utils` subpackage contains functionality such as test helper functions. The `classes` subpackage contains the machinery for our base data structures.

Organizational development and planning

We will begin this initiative by building a coalition of plasma physicists and external experts to guide the creation of this software ecosystem. This coalition should include representation from heliophysics, plasma astrophysics, laboratory plasma physics, magnetic fusion energy, high energy density physics, and basic plasma physics. This group should contain educators, observers, numericists, theorists, experimentalists, and computer scientists. Each participating experimental facility should have at least one representative. An early goal of this coalition will be to select representative use cases from the plasma community as a whole in order to plan future development and design overall software architecture.

We will hold a series of in-person development meetings. Each meeting should begin with tutorials and a discussion of the current status of PlasmaPy for new contributors and students. Participants in the first meeting will collaborate on a software requirements specification and a roadmap for future development. These meetings should include unconference sessions and end with a coding sprint to enable participants to begin implementing the plans and ideas that come up earlier in the week and to make their first code contributions.

These tasks will enable us to complete a code development roadmap, design the software architecture, and begin implementation of these community-developed plans.

Code development priorities

Here we succinctly summarize a subset of the high priority PlasmaPy development tasks. For more detail, please refer to the recently awarded proposal by [Murphy et al. \(2019c\)](#).

Refactor existing code

A common scientific code development practice is to prioritize adding new features while making few improvements to existing code. This approach allows [technical debt](#) to accumulate, especially when new code depends on fragile existing code. Some technical debt exists in PlasmaPy, especially for early contributions to the project before our development practices were codified. We will begin this initiative by a period of refactoring in order to provide a solid foundation for future code development and to give an opportunity for new contributors to learn about the package structure and our development practices.

Improve tests and testing capabilities

Test code is equally as important as production code (e.g., Martin 2009). Test suites that are absent or hastily written act as change preventers. Modifying code without tests risks introducing hidden bugs with no practical way of tracking them down (e.g., Feathers 2005). If tests are difficult to read or modify, programmers may avoid altering production code to avoid the frustration of updating poorly written tests. A high quality testing framework makes production code more flexible since we can make changes without fear of introducing hidden bugs. We will improve our testing infrastructure and refactor tests that were written early on.

Expand implementation of high level data structures

One of the most fundamental design decisions in PlasmaPy is how to represent different plasmas. This decision is challenging given that plasma data comes from many different sources in many different formats with many different conventions for metadata. Our approach (Leonard 2018) is based on SunPy's `Map` class factory. We created an abstract base class (ABC) to define the high level application programming interface (API) for different plasma representations. This class can be subclassed for different plasmas so long as the abstract methods in the ABC are implemented. The `Plasma` class factory will then select the appropriate subclass based on the type of input or data set. PlasmaPy's Google Summer of Code student in 2018 implemented the machinery for the `Plasma` class. We will expand this implementation as metadata standards and open access plasma data sets become available.

Add fluid and kinetic dispersion relation solvers

When a plasma in equilibrium is perturbed, it develops different waves and instabilities depending on different parameters. The normal modes of a plasma are generally described by a frequency vs. wavenumber related called the dispersion relation. The dispersion relation solvers that currently exist are written for many different programming languages, though these often lack interoperability with other plasma analysis software. We will therefore add general purpose dispersion relation solvers to PlasmaPy and emphasize usability and interoperability.

Implement experimental data analysis tools

We will provide a comprehensive set of classes for analyzing data collected by commonly deployed diagnostics while creating documentation that covers class functionality, provides educational information about each diagnostic, and describes how members of the plasma community can develop diagnostic classes themselves. The goal of PlasmaPy will not be to provide data reduction and analysis pipelines for particular experiments, but rather to provide toolkits that can be used by experimentalists to develop these pipelines themselves. For example, we may create a class that broadly represents a type of probe. That class could then be instantiated to represent a specific diagnostic on a particular device.

We will develop base classes for commonly used plasma diagnostics such as Langmuir probes (including swept probes, triple probes, double probes, and Mach probes) and magnetic flux (b-dot) probes in the early stages of the initiative. As time progresses, we will add classes to represent further diagnostics including but not limited to emissive probes, velocity analyzers,

Thomson scattering, and laser-induced fluorescence. We will make each class intuitively configurable for the properties of the diagnostic.

Include flexible plasma simulation capabilities²

The PlasmaPy software ecosystem requires a wide variety of plasma simulation capabilities using fluid, kinetic, and hybrid approximations with multiple numerical methods. Code development should equally prioritize usability, reliability, maintainability, and performance.

We will develop abstract interfaces to enable different problem setups, physical models, and numerical methods to be decoupled from each other as much as possible. We will develop a standard for representing the problem setup independently of the physical model and numerical method. Creating such a boundary with an abstract interface will provide a clear separation of responsibility between the problem specification and the numerics. We will develop abstract interfaces for the numerical methods, physical models, and simulation results. These abstractions will allow users to write the same high-level code while hiding the details of the implementation. Each numerical method should have its own module that is interchangeable with other numerical methods.

Most plasma simulation software is written in low-level compiled languages such as Fortran and C. While these languages offer excellent performance, development can be significantly slower because these languages are not interactive and types must be declared. [Julia](#) is a new high-level interactive dynamically typed language that uses just-in-time compilation with type inference and multiple dispatch to achieve performance comparable to Fortran, even without type declarations ([Bezanson et al. 2017](#)). Julia natively supports parallelization and has been used at petascale ([Regier et al. 2019](#)). These language features greatly speed up code development and optimization by allowing prototyping in the same language used for performance runs. Julia can be called from Python and Python can be called from Julia, so these languages can coexist in a single ecosystem. We plan to write numerical simulation tools for this software ecosystem in Julia. Both Python and Julia can call C and Fortran code, so this simulation framework can include interfaces to existing code.

Programmatic Benefit

An open source software ecosystem for plasma physics will (1) make research more open and accessible; (2) build reproducibility into research workflows; (3) increase the efficiency of research; (4) reduce unnecessary and costly duplication of functionality; (5) improve the quality of plasma physics software; (6) reduce barriers to entry to plasma physics research; (7) enable students to make quicker progress on their first research projects; (8) provide researchers with well-documented, well-tested, well-maintained, and continuously updated software; (9) introduce students to collaborative code development practices; (10) provide opportunities for students, scientists, and engineers to learn and implement knowledge from computer science; (11) improve interoperability between different packages; (12) reduce software development

² The numerical simulation code development tasks described here are very much in line with the initiative proposed by Vay et al. (2019) to create an integrated ecosystem of plasma simulation tools.

startup costs for new experiments; (13) enable greater cross-device and cross-disciplinary collaborations; (14) facilitate intergenerational transfer of knowledge; and (15) provide software tools for educators to introduce plasma physics concepts to students.

US Leadership and Global Context

The development of an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics will promote international scientific collaboration while keeping the US at the forefront of plasma research.

Timeline of the Initiative

The PlasmaPy core package has already been developed through version 0.2.0. We anticipate that version 1.0.0 will be completed within ~3–5 years.

Science and Technology Readiness

Development of PlasmaPy is already underway. We know of no significant scientific or technological barriers to an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics.

Community Preparedness

Despite the lack of scientific and technological barriers, there are barriers related to programmatic considerations, institutional policies, the culture of the field, and common research practices. We make the following recommendations.

Invest in open source software development and maintenance

A longstanding problem has been that funding agencies have few mechanisms to support the development and maintenance of research software infrastructure (e.g., [Muna et al. 2016](#)). The available opportunities are highly competitive and unable to meet community needs. We recommend that agencies create a funding opportunity to support collaborative community development of an open source software ecosystem for plasma research and education. For example, NASA's [Heliophysics Data Environment Emphasis](#) opportunity was repurposed to provide seed funding for the development of an open source Python ecosystem for heliophysics. Awardees should be required to collaborate with each other to promote interoperability, fill gaps in functionality, and reduce duplication of effort. Projects that become essential should be supported by contracts to facilitate software sustainability.

Make plasma data open access

Few data sets from laboratory plasma experiments and plasma simulations are open access. Barriers to accessing plasma data sets make our research less reproducible and make it more difficult to develop open research software infrastructure. The creation of an online portal to access plasma data sets akin to the [Virtual Solar Observatory](#) would facilitate greater openness and scientific reproducibility. If this portal has a well-defined API, then the software ecosystem could create tools to find and download plasma data sets. Data should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (e.g., [FAIR guiding principles](#); [Wilkinson et al. 2016](#)).

Create open plasma metadata standards

The development of general purpose plasma analysis software is made much more difficult by the dire shortage of open metadata schemas. The plasma community should collaboratively develop metadata standards to describe experimental data and simulation input/output (see also the initiative by Vay et al. 2019). These metadata standards should be versioned and archived on a platform such as [Zenodo](#) so that each version is citable. Example metadata models include [openPMD](#) (Huebl et al. 2018) and the [SPASE metadata model](#) (Roberts et al. 2018).

Engage with external experts

The development of a research software ecosystem requires the application of knowledge from computer science, data science, information science, open source project management, and science education. Domain experts from plasma physics should collaborate with experts from these disciplines in order to develop the next generation of software tools.

Streamline the process of making codes open source

Institutions should enact policies that enable researchers to quickly release software under an open source license. Policies should not require researchers to undertake multiple steps over several months to openly release software. The conditions under which export control must be considered should be clearly defined. Policies should explicitly allow contributions to external open source projects when export control is not applicable.

Cultivate a culture of open community software development

Plasma physics should change from the “roll your own” paradigm of software development to the open development model pioneered by projects like Astropy. We should take time to learn collaborative code development skills, data management techniques, and automation of analysis workflows. Institutions should organize Software Carpentry workshops to teach skills usually neglected in coursework such as shell scripting, version control, and Python programming. Undergraduate and graduate programs in plasma physics should incorporate training in these skills into coursework, and perhaps even offer courses on computer science for physical scientists. Meetings on Python in plasma physics should be held annually.

Cost Range

Muna et al. (2016) used an industry standard tool to estimate that reproducing Astropy through version ~1.2.1 would take ~23 developers working full-time for ~2.5 years and cost ~\$8.5M. We anticipate that the development of essential functionality in the PlasmaPy ecosystem will require a comparable amount of effort, much of which will be spread out across the plasma community.

The full cost of the software ecosystem (including plasma simulation capabilities) depends on the number of affiliated packages to be developed and is hard to predict. Any funding opportunity to support the development of an open source research software infrastructure should require that awardees work together to create coding and documentation standards,

ensure interoperability, fill gaps in functionality, and reduce duplication of functionality. This collaboration may be started by creating the plasma physics equivalents to the [Python in Astronomy conference series](#) and the [Python in Heliophysics Community](#).

The total cost of this initiative may seem like a large investment when consolidated into one place. However, this investment of time and effort has already been happening, but in a distributed and inefficient way. Funding that is allocated to projects like PlasmaPy will be more visible than this distributed effort, but by providing a central focus, this initiative will make a wide portfolio of other projects more efficient.

Fortunately, DOE would not be the sole funding agency to support the development of this software ecosystem. The NSF Cyberinfrastructure for Sustained Scientific Innovation (CSSI) program recently awarded a five-year \$2.4M collaborative proposal submitted by [Murphy et al. \(2019c\)](#) to develop core functionality in an open source software ecosystem for plasma research and education.³ The award team includes representatives from laboratory plasma physics, heliophysics, and plasma astrophysics across four institutions. The activities that fall within the scope of the CSSI award do not require DOE funding in order to be performed.

The caveat with this NSF award is that it specifically excludes code development activities that are solely related to fusion energy sciences (FES), as this field is traditionally funded by DOE/FES rather than NSF.⁴ Consequently, some investment by DOE/FES will be necessary in order for the FES community to fully participate in this software ecosystem. In particular, DOE should fund members of the FES community who are not covered by the CSSI award to perform FES-specific and other code development activities that are beyond the scope of the CSSI award. Because of the opportunity for synergy with an NSF-funded project, participation in this initiative will be a bargain for DOE/FES that would maximize the return on investment of the NSF CSSI award.

Cross-Cutting Connections

Workforce Development

An open source software ecosystem for plasma physics will reduce barriers to entry for newcomers to our field by providing clear documentation, access to an active community of users and developers, and an intuitive interface. Such an ecosystem will let students get off to a head start on their first research projects; they will no longer need to rewrite functionality that already exists but is hard to read, difficult to modify, or inadequately documented. Students and scientists alike will be introduced to collaborative code development practices. Recent plasma

³ We have uploaded the NSF CSSI proposal submitted by [Murphy et al. \(2019c\)](#) (including the panel summary, reviewer comments, and responses from the proposal team) to the Zenodo archival website so that it may be used as an open community resource. The full scope of the CSSI award may be ascertained from this document. Consequently, plasma scientists will be able to propose activities that complement rather than overlap what has already been funded.

⁴ While the NSF CSSI award will not support code development activities solely related to FES, it does contain funding to “coordinate with and provide user support to members of the FES community, including those who wish to develop affiliated packages.”

graduates who enter industry upon graduation will have an advantage in the job search if they have experience with Python and collaborative code development. This software ecosystem should include educational materials such as tutorials and Jupyter notebooks to simultaneously introduce core concepts in plasma physics and how to use PlasmaPy. Documentation will introduce not just how a class or function works but also the plasma physics concepts behind it. Students using PlasmaPy will have connections to other institutions and researchers through the community that naturally develops around an open source software ecosystem.

Measurement and Diagnostics

PlasmaPy provides an opportunity to develop robust diagnostic reduction and analysis software tools that are reviewed by a diverse user base and tested against a wide parameter space. The `diagnostics` subpackage of PlasmaPy will contain base classes for each category of diagnostic. These classes could then be subclassed, customized, and instantiated by experimentalists to represent particular diagnostics in different devices. Because of the breadth of the plasma diagnostics in use, the PlasmaPy core package will probably not contain the data reduction tools for different devices, but rather it will contain well-tested building blocks for data reduction pipelines that are common among multiple devices. The use of abstract base classes would provide a common API for analyses of different probes of similar types. These tools will reduce the software development overhead costs needed to begin new experiments, in particular at small colleges.

Theory & Computation

There are likely hundreds of plasma simulation software packages being used for scientific research. Each simulation package usually solves a particular class of equations with a particular numerical method for a particular set of applications within a narrow scientific subfield. Many of these codes lack a modular design and are lacking flexibility. Each code has its own particular way of specifying initial conditions (ICs), boundary conditions (BCs), and the computational domain. Performing a benchmark between two codes often requires two expert users spending weeks to make sure that the ICs and BCs are consistent with each other. Plasma physics needs an integrated ecosystem of advanced simulation tools for plasma modeling (e.g., Vay et al. 2019). PlasmaPy provides an opportunity to develop these tools as part of the same software ecosystem used to analyze experimental results. PlasmaPy could include an abstract interface to handle post-processing, visualization, and analysis tasks in a flexible modern way. PlasmaPy could also include an interface to enable the same problem setup to be used with multiple numerical methods. These capabilities will benefit software packages by making them more accessible and user-friendly for students and researchers.

Enabling Technology

A software ecosystem for plasma physics will increase efficiency and improve the reproducibility of plasma research. Cross-experiment and data science efforts will be less difficult when different experiments use the same software to analyze data sets with the same open metadata

standards. A software ecosystem for plasma physics will reduce software development costs associated with building new experiments.

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Appendix: Response to Expert Group Evaluation

The advocates should clarify what limitations (if any) there are on making various codes and tools open source, especially in the context of international and public-private collaborations.

To the best of our knowledge, all current and planned PlasmaPy code development activities fall under the Fundamental Research Exclusion to export controls.

PlasmaPy is released under a permissive (rather than copyleft) open source license. There are no restrictions on commercial use, as any such restrictions would break compatibility with the [Open Source Definition](#). Users have the right to create derivative works and release them under the same or different licenses (including proprietary licenses), as long as a copy of the original license is provided. In contrast, a copyleft license only allows derivative works to be released under the same license, which often makes businesses wary of using copyleft software. The choice of a permissive license maximizes the potential for use by industry. Moreover, businesses across the nation widely use and contribute to open source software because doing so is often highly beneficial to their business interests. An open source software ecosystem for plasma science has the potential to bridge fundamental research and commercial applications.

Additional information on how PlasmaPy could connect or integrate with other ongoing computational initiatives such as framework tools described in the initiatives by Smith et al, Vay et al, Ying et al, and Cueno et al. would be useful.

The initiatives for an integrated ecosystem of advanced simulation tools (Vay et al. 2019), OMFIT (Smith et al. 2019), and PlasmaPy could all fit into a broader strategic element such as: *Invest in open source software infrastructure to streamline plasma research and improve scientific reproducibility.*

The initiative by Vay et al. is highly aligned with the goals of our initiative. We have previously been in contact with developers from openPMD and the Particle-In-Cell Modeling Interface, and have implemented openPMD as the first subclass of PlasmaPy's `Plasma` abstract base class. Many of the suggestions made by Vay et al. could be included in the PlasmaPy software ecosystem by working together to enforce interoperability. A short-term goal of PlasmaPy is to

develop classes and metadata standards to represent initial conditions, boundary conditions, and the computational domain for plasma simulations. These classes and standards could be used in conjunction with the tools proposed in the Vay et al. initiative in support of interoperability between the simulation initiatives of Ying et al., Cuneo et al., Bhattacharjee et al., and others.

A potential link between OMFIT and PlasmaPy is through the Ordered Multidimensional Array Structure (OMAS) that is being developed by the OMFIT community to provide an interface to ITER's Integrated Modeling and Analysis Suite. Because OMAS is being developed under a permissive open source license, it could be used within PlasmaPy to access future ITER data.